

ASSESSING THE PRACTICE OF HEALTH, SAFETY, AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY ON CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN LAGOS STATE: IMPACTS, FACTORS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Husseini Musa

ABSTRACT

This research aims to assess the practice of health, safety, and environmental policy on construction projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study population consisted of Quantity Surveyors, Architects, Engineers, and consultants in the construction industry. The research used both primary and secondary data sources, and the data were analyzed using frequency and percentages. The results revealed that the level of use of health, safety, and environmental policy by organizations and construction professionals was high. The study also identified the factors affecting the implementation of the practice of health, safety, and environmental policy, including ineffective planning, poor communication, and a lack of commitment and concern for workers. The research recommends that organizations should be screened properly to eliminate firms that don't comply with health and safety policy, there should be a review of health and safety policy objectives, and proper planning methods should be adopted from the inception of the project to prevent accidents and injuries. Training and seminars should also be organized on health and safety to create better awareness amongst participants in the built environment and improve the current state of health and safety in Lagos state.

Keywords: Health, Safety, Environmental, Policy, Construction projects, Accident

1.1 Introduction to the Study

The construction sector plays a crucial role in the economic development of any country, as it accounts for a significant portion of investments in development plans. Although the industry has become more mechanized, it still employs a large percentage of the labor force, ranging from 9 to 12 percent and occasionally up to 20 percent (International Labour Office, 1995). The intricate nature of construction tasks and the work environment expose workers to various health and safety hazards, making construction sites dangerous. As a result, enhancing occupational safety and health is vital for the construction sector.

Idoro, (2009) emphasizes the need for government support in the construction industry by establishing and enforcing legislations that govern health and safety practices. Effective safety, health, and working conditions are dependent on collaboration among governments, employers, and workers. These policies aim to shift the mindset of employers (and employees) towards health and safety by providing comprehensive legislative frameworks, incorporating general duties, and fostering an organized approach to workplace safety.

1.2 Problem Statement

The construction industry is known for being hazardous. Workplace fatalities and severe injuries are common occurrences, particularly among construction workers. Diugwu et al., (2012) argue that the inadequate regulation of health and safety across various sectors of the economy is primarily due to an ineffective health and safety law. Furthermore, the absence of an institutional framework for overseeing construction activities and insufficient enforcement of health and safety policies and procedures contribute to poor health and safety conditions on construction sites (Laryea et al., 2010).

1.3 Research Questions

This research aims to address the following questions:

1. Which factors may influence the implementation of Health, Safety, and Environmental policies in Lagos State?
2. How extensively are Health, Safety, and Environmental policies used in Lagos State?

1.4 Aim and Objectives

The primary goal of this study is to evaluate the application of Health, Safety, and Environmental policies in construction projects within Lagos state. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To pinpoint the factors that impact the application of Health, Safety, and Environmental policies in Lagos state's construction projects.
2. To gauge the extent to which various Health and Safety policies are used in construction projects in Lagos state.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research contributes to the development of building projects nationally and serves as a valuable resource for client organizations, construction consultants, government officials, and the general public. The study aims to inform building project stakeholders about the evaluation of Health, Safety, and Environmental policy practices and to identify factors influencing their implementation in Lagos state. This research is crucial as it assesses the application of Health, Safety, and Environmental policies, which will aid stakeholders in creating a secure working environment.

1.6 Hypothesis of the Study

Hypothesis H0: There is a significant difference between the factors affecting implementing health, safety, and environmental policy practices in construction projects.

Hypothesis H1: There is no significant difference between the factors affecting the implementation of health, safety, and environmental policy practices in construction projects.

1.7 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This research examines the application of Health, Safety, and Environmental policies in construction projects in Lagos state. It encompasses building project stakeholders such as clients, building contractors, and construction consultants like project managers, quantity surveyors, architects, and engineers. The study is restricted to residential and commercial buildings in Lagos state, selected due to the high concentration of building professionals, consultants, and the increasing number of building projects in the state.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to address Objective 1: To identify the impact of Health and Safety policy on construction project performance, and Objective 2: To determine the extent to which Health and Safety policy influences the overall construction industry. To do so, it discusses the importance of Health and Safety policy, the role of stakeholders in promoting Health and Safety, and the effect of such policy on construction project performance and the construction industry.

2.2 Importance of Health and Safety Policy in Construction

Health and Safety policy is of paramount importance in construction projects because it safeguards the well-being of individuals involved in construction activities (Laryea & Mensah, 2010). The construction industry is inherently hazardous, with a high rate of accidents, injuries, and fatalities compared to other industries. Therefore, it is vital to implement robust Health and Safety policies to minimize these risks and ensure the welfare of workers, contractors, clients, and the public. The implementation of Health and Safety policies contributes to several positive outcomes in construction projects, such as:

1. **Minimizing accidents and injuries:** By identifying and addressing potential hazards, Health and Safety policies help reduce the occurrence of accidents and injuries, creating a safer work environment for all involved (Famakin & Fawehinmi, 2012).
2. **Legal compliance:** Health and Safety policies help construction companies comply with relevant laws and regulations, thus avoiding penalties, fines, and legal repercussions. This compliance is essential for maintaining a good reputation and ensuring business continuity.
3. **Improved working conditions:** Health and Safety policies aim to improve the overall working conditions for construction workers, including adequate training, personal protective equipment, and ergonomic considerations. These improvements lead to increased worker satisfaction and reduced turnover rates.
4. **Cost savings:** By reducing accidents and injuries, Health and Safety policies contribute to cost savings through lower medical expenses, workers' compensation claims, and insurance premiums. Additionally, a safer work environment results in fewer work stoppages, leading to increased productivity and reduced project delays.
5. **Enhanced reputation:** Construction companies that prioritize Health and Safety are more likely to be perceived as responsible and reliable by clients, investors, and the public (Kheni et al., 2008). This positive perception can lead to better market performance, increased client satisfaction, and a competitive edge in the industry.
6. **Sustainable development:** Health and Safety policies contribute to sustainable development by promoting the responsible use of resources, reducing waste, and minimizing the environmental impact of construction activities. This approach is in line with the growing emphasis on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in the construction industry.

2.3 Challenges and Barriers to Implementing Health and Safety Policies in Construction

Despite the clear benefits of implementing Health and Safety policies in construction projects, there are numerous challenges and barriers that construction companies and stakeholders face. These challenges can hinder the effective implementation of Health and Safety measures, leading to increased risks and negative consequences. Some of the main challenges and barriers include:

1. **Lack of awareness and understanding:** Many construction workers, especially those in developing countries or small-scale projects, may not be fully aware of the importance of Health and Safety policies (Kheni et al., 2008). This lack of understanding can result in non-compliance and insufficient implementation of safety measures.
2. **Insufficient resources:** Implementing Health and Safety policies requires investment in training, personal protective equipment, and other safety measures (Adetayo & Onatayo, 2023). Smaller construction companies or those operating in low-resource settings may struggle to allocate the necessary funds for these investments (Famakin & Fawehinmi, 2012).
3. **Inadequate enforcement:** In some regions, the enforcement of Health and Safety regulations may be weak or non-existent due to a lack of regulatory oversight, corruption, or insufficient resources dedicated to inspections and enforcement (Laryea & Mensah, 2010). This lack of enforcement can lead to a culture of non-compliance and increased risk for construction workers.
4. **Cultural factors:** In certain cultures, there may be a prevailing attitude that accidents are inevitable or that taking risks is part of the job, leading to a reluctance to adopt Health and Safety measures (Kheni et al., 2008). Overcoming these cultural barriers is crucial for promoting a culture of safety in the construction industry.
5. **Complex supply chains:** The construction industry often involves multiple contractors, subcontractors, and suppliers, which can make it challenging to ensure consistent Health and Safety standards across the entire project (Famakin & Fawehinmi, 2012). Clear communication and coordination among all parties are essential for overcoming this challenge.
6. **Resistance to change:** Implementing Health and Safety policies may require significant changes in work processes, equipment, and training. Some workers or managers may resist

these changes due to a fear of the unknown or a belief that the existing methods are sufficient (Kheni et al., 2008).

2.4 The Importance of Training and Education in Health and Safety Implementation

Training and education are vital components in the successful implementation of Health and Safety policies within the construction industry. The development of a strong safety culture and the reduction of risks depend on a well-informed and well-trained workforce. Some key aspects of training and education in Health and Safety include:

1. **Awareness and understanding:** Comprehensive training programs can increase the awareness and understanding of Health and Safety regulations, policies, and best practices among construction workers, supervisors, and managers (Rowlinson, 2004). This knowledge forms the foundation for proper implementation and adherence to safety measures.
2. **Skill development:** Effective training helps workers develop the necessary skills to identify potential hazards, use protective equipment correctly, and follow safe work procedures (Famakin & Fawehinmi, 2012). These skills are essential for maintaining a safe work environment and reducing the risk of accidents.
3. **Behavioral change:** Training and education can help shift attitudes and behaviors, fostering a culture of safety and responsibility among construction workers (Kheni et al., 2008). This change in mindset is critical for ensuring that safety policies are consistently applied and that workers prioritize their own safety and the safety of their colleagues (Oladiran et al., 2019).
4. **Legal compliance:** Adequate training ensures that construction companies and their employees are aware of and comply with local, national, and international Health and Safety regulations (Laryea & Mensah, 2010). Compliance with these regulations is crucial for avoiding legal penalties and potential reputational damage.
5. **Continuous improvement:** Regular training and education can help construction workers stay up-to-date with the latest Health and Safety best practices, innovations, and technologies (Rowlinson, 2004). This ongoing learning process supports the continuous improvement of safety measures and reduces the likelihood of accidents (Onososen et al., 2023).

6. Enhanced productivity and profitability: When workers are well-trained in Health and Safety, they are more likely to work efficiently and effectively, leading to increased productivity and profitability for construction companies (Famakin & Fawehinmi, 2012). A safe work environment also reduces the likelihood of project delays due to accidents, injuries, or regulatory violations (Oladiran & Onatayo, 2019).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This chapter briefly explains the procedure used in carrying out the study and the subsequent analysis of the results obtained. It includes a brief description of the study population, sampling method and size, the process through which the questionnaire was developed and administered. It also includes the techniques used in analysing the data generated for the study. Nevertheless, the limitations of the methodology are also enumerated.

3.1. THE STUDY POPULATION

The target population for the purpose of this study was Quantity Surveyors, Architects, Engineers and consultants in the construction industry.

3.2 SAMPLING METHOD AND SIZE

Generally, sample selection and sample size were based on statistical analysis, mainly with the use of frequency and percentages. The sample units were drawn from the professionals: Architect, Engineers, Quantity Surveyors (i.e. contractors and consultants) in the southwest zone of Nigeria. The sample size was a total of 30.

3.3 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data used for this study were from two sources, primary and secondary data. The primary data were derived from the structured questionnaires administered to respondents, while the secondary data comprises related literatures to the study.

3.4 THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The questionnaire was designed to provide answers to the objectives enumerated in chapter one. It consists of multiple-choice questions and was divided into two sections, Section A dealt with the

background of the respective respondents and covered issues like personal information and place of work. Section B dealt with general questions on the study.

3.5 METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

The method employed is the use of frequency and percentages. This procedure was aimed at establishing the percentages of both the impacts of Health, Safety and Environmental policy on construction project, the factors that may affect the implementation of the practice of Health, Safety and Environmental policy. The questionnaire gave each respondent an opportunity to the factors that may affect the implementation of the practice of Health, Safety and Environmental policy and its effect on construction project. On the basis of this percentages by the various groups. It was possible to identify the most likely factors affecting the implementation of the practice of Health, Safety and Environmental policy.

3.6 CONSTRAINTS IN DATA COLLECTION

The problems encountered during the course of the survey are enumerated below.

- a) There was the problem of getting quick response from the respondents, as they treated such questionnaire with levity.
- b) Some of the respondents were too busy to treat the questionnaires.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS

Data collected from the questionnaire responses are analysed and presented here in tables and figures. The presentation is in order of appearance of the questions in the research questionnaires.

Table 4.2.1: DEMOGRAPHIC CHARATERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Type of organization	Frequency	Percent
Aron	4	13.3
El-Alan	2	6.7
Acetek	3	10.0

Qs consult	3	10.0
Charter bridge	2	6.7
Beton Bau	4	13.3
Sea surveyors	2	6.7
Dalkirk	2	6.7
FOAB partnership	2	6.7
Energo Building	2	6.7
Feldom	4	13.3
Total	30	100

Table 4.2.1 above indicates the result of the analysis from the questionnaire, it is observed that out of 30 respondents that were used for the study, 7 were from consultant and 23 were from contracting organizations. Hence majority of the respondents were from contracting organizations.

Table 4.2.2	Category of organization	
	Frequency	Percent
Indigenous	28	93.3
Multinational	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.2 above shows the category of the organization, 93.3% of the respondents work in indigenous companies and 6.7% of the respondents work in multinational companies. This infers that majority of the respondents work in indigenous companies in Lagos state.

Table 4.2.3 Years of organization existence

	Frequency	Percent
Above 10 years	30	100.0
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.3 above shows that all the respondents work for organization that has been existing for more than 10 years with 100% of the respondents acknowledging this.

Table 4.2.4 Professional background

	Frequency	Percent
Building	18	60.0
Civil engineer	2	6.7
QS	10	33.3
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.4 above shows that majority of the respondents are builders with 60%, 33.3% of the respondents being quantity surveyors and 6.7% of the respondents are civil engineers. This infers that most respondents are builders who can give better information on awareness of health and safety on construction project.

Table 4.2.5 Academic qualification

	Frequency	Percent
HND	6	20.0
B.Sc	22	73.3

M,Sc	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.5 shows that majority of the respondents are B.Sc. holders with 73.3% of the respondents acknowledging this, 20% are HND certificate holders from polytechnics and the remaining 6.7% are M.Sc. holders. This infers that most respondents are well educated and knowledgeable enough to give precise information on their level of educational Qualification.

	Frequency	Percent
less than 5 years	7	23.3
6-10	12	40.0
11-15	11	36.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.6 depicts that 40% of the respondents have been in the construction industry for 6 to 10 years, 36.7% of the respondents have been in the industry between 11 to 15 years and 23.3% of the remaining respondents have been in the construction industry for less than 5 years. This shows that respondents with the working experience of 6-10 years gave adequate information.

	Frequency	Percent
Member	14	46.7
Graduate	4	13.3
Corporate	8	26.7
Fellow	1	3.3
Associate	3	10.0

Total	30	100.0
-------	----	-------

Table 4.2.7 shows that 46.7% of the respondents are members, 26.7% of the respondents are corporate, 13.3% of the remaining respondents are graduate, and 3.3% of the respondents are fellows. It is deduced from this result that most of the respondents of their respective professional bodies are members.

Table 4.2.8 Professional bodies

	Frequency	Percent
NIOB	18	60.0
NIQS	10	33.3
NSE	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 4.2.8 above shows the professional body to which my respondents are registered, with 60% of the respondents belonging to NIOB, 33.3% belonging to NIQS and NSE having the least with a mere 6.7% of the respondents as members.

Table 4.2.9: Frequency of use of health and safety policy

Frequency of use	Mean	Rank
Awareness of health and safety policy	0.84	1
Do you comply with own health and safety policy	0.75	2
Management control	0.75	2
Provision of welfare facilities	0.73	4
Management commitment	0.72	5
Level of workers compliance with safety standard	0.72	5
Do you carryout hazard identification and work assessment	0.71	7
Do you review health and safety policy objectives	0.70	8

Do you provide adequate training for workers	0.70	8
Do you assign responsibilities for monitoring compliance	0.69	10
Do you communicate with workers to address health and safety	0.69	10
Adequacy of health and safety regulations	0.69	10
Do you have arrangement for reviewing health and safety performance	0.66	12
Management attitude toward health and safety	0.66	12

4.2.1: Frequency of use of health and safety policy

Based on the results of analysis, the mean of their assessment and overall ranking of the frequency of use of health and safety policy have been established as shown in table 4.9. Respondent were asked to assess how often they are used on projects. Fourteen variables were identified, ranked and analyzed. The top five most used health and safety policy are Awareness of health and safety policy with MIS of 0.84, Do you comply with own health and safety policy with MIS 0.75, Management control with MIS 0.75, Provision of welfare facilities with MIS 0.73, Management commitment with MIS 0.72, Level of workers compliance with safety standard with MIS 0.72. This survey now reveals that Awareness of health and safety policy is the most frequently used health and safety policy. This now provided solution to the second objective of the study which is to assess the frequency of use of health and safety policy on construction project in Lagos State.

4.2.2 Factors affecting the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy on construction project.

Hypothesis H0: there is significant difference between the factors that affects the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy on construction project.

Hypothesis H1: there is no significant difference between the factors that affects the

implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy on construction project.

Table 4.2.10

	Variable	Asymp sig (2sided)
1	Organization do not show commitment and concern for all workers on site * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.25
2	Organization do not show commitment and concern for all workers on site * Inadequate government support	0.01
3	Inadequate funding * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.02
4	Inadequate funding * Inadequate government support	0.00
5	Lack of basic resources and training opportunities for site workers * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.00
6	Lack of basic resources and training opportunities for site workers * Inadequate government support	0.00
7	Ineffective institutional framework responsible for health and safety * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.00
8	Ineffective institutional framework responsible for health and safety * Inadequate government support	0.00
9	Shortage of competent personnel * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.04
10	Shortage of competent personnel * Inadequate government support	0.65
11	Inability of workers to interpret written health and safety policy * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.02
12	Inability of workers to interpret written health and safety policy * Inadequate government support	0.00
13	Poor communication and coordination * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.00

14	Poor communication and coordination * Inadequate government support	0.00
15	Ineffective planning * Ineffective enforcement strategies	0.41
16	Ineffective planning * Inadequate government support	0.11
	Total	0.09

Table 4.2.10 reveals descriptive statistics (mean item score) and Pearson correlation coefficients of the variables. This survey now reveals that the significant value for the chi-square test was found to be approximately 0.09. Since 0.09 is greater than 0.05, H1 (Null hypothesis) is accepted and H0 (Alternative hypothesis) is rejected. It implies that there is no significant difference between the factors that affects the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy. The survey also shows that Ineffective planning is the highest factor affecting the implementation of the practice of health and safety policy. Which now addresses the first objective of the study.

4.3 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This chapter has been able to present the analysis of data according to the objectives of the study. Summarily the analysis of the data presented the following results to the objectives. The most common factor affecting the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy is ineffective planning. It was expected that organization do not show commitment would be one of the major factor affecting the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy on building project, but it has been affirmed by the respondent that ineffective planning is the major factor affecting the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy on building project. The results of the study suggest that there is no significant difference between the factors that affects the implementation of the practice of health, safety and environmental policy.

The research also shows that the level of use of health, safety and environmental policy is high with respondents agreeing that there is proper awareness of health and safety policy, management control, and compliance with own health and safety policy in their respective organization.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The study's results demonstrate that all research objectives were achieved, and the gathered information addressed the entire set of objectives established at the research's onset. This study examined the level of adoption, and factors influencing the implementation of health, safety, and environmental policies on construction projects in Lagos State. Since Lagos State is one of the most populous states in the country, it can serve as a basis for assessing the nation. The research also revealed that the level of adoption of health, safety, and environmental policies by organizations and construction professionals (consultants and contractors) is high. The survey identified the three highest-ranked factors affecting the implementation of health, safety, and environmental policies on building projects as ineffective planning, poor communication, and organizations' lack of commitment and concern for workers. The research suggests improved training and better communication, increased efficiency and effectiveness in planning and monitoring policies, and post-implementation reviews as measures to enhance the practice of health and safety policies on construction projects.

Based on the research conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The construction industry should ensure that organizations are thoroughly evaluated to eliminate firms that do not comply with health and safety policies.
2. Health and safety policy objectives should be reviewed periodically.
3. The study revealed that ineffective planning is a significant factor affecting health and safety policies. Therefore, proper planning methods should be adopted from a project's

inception to prevent accidents and injuries on construction projects.

REFERENCES

Adetayo, O.; Onatayo, D. A Scientometric Review of Bim in Facility Management Research.

Preprints.org 2023, 2023030095. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202303.0095.v1>.

Davis k. (N.D) How to develop a health and safety policy. *E-how contributor, ehow.com*

Diugwu, Baba and Egila (2012) Effective regulation and level of awareness, an expose of the Nigeria's Construction Industry. *Journal of science and technology*, pg 140-146

Duncan E. (2006) How to develop a health and safety policy. *E-how contributor, ehow.com*

Equalities impact assessment (2008) Health, safety and wellbeing strategy and policy. *Equalities impact assessment, Department of corporate resources, January, Pg 2-8*

Famakin and Fawehinmi (2012) Quantity surveyor's perception of Construction health and safety regulation in Nigeria. *Journal of building performance volume 3 issue 1*

International Labour Office (1995) A Global Strategy: Promoting safety and Health at Work. *The ILO Report for World Day for Safety and Health at Work*, International Labour Office, Geneva, 2005.

Health and safety executive (2011) Successful health and safety management *Second edition ISBN 978 0 7176 1276 5, Pg 7-8*

Holt A.J (2006) Principles of construction safety *second edition Pg 47-49*

Idoro G.I (2009) Health and Safety performance of the Nigerian Construction Industry and the achievement of the millennium development goals. *Punch on the web, October 2011*.

Laryea and Mensah (2010) Health and Safety on Construction sites in Ghana, *Being a conference or workshop item presented at The construction, building and Real estate research conference of the Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors at Dauphine Universite', Paris, France. September 2010, pg 9*

National work experience partnership group (2006) Health and Safety assessment for work experience placements - a good practice guide *version 1 pg 13-22*

Okeola O.G (2009) Occupational Health and Safety assessment in the Construction Industry. *Presented at the 1st annual civil engineering conference, University of illorin, Nigeria. Civil engineering impact on national development. Pg 239*

Oladiran and Sotunbo (2009) Accidents on building sites: rate of occurrence and causes

Oladiran, Olatunji & Onatayo, Damilola. (2019). Labour productivity: Perception of site managers on building projects. *LAUTECH Journal of Civil and Environmental Studies*. 2. 10.36108/laujoces/9102/20(0110).

Oladiran, Olatunji & Onatayo, Damilola. (2018). Evaluating Change Orders and their Impacts on Construction Project Performance in Lagos, Nigeria. *FUTY Journal of the Environment*. 12. 81-89.

Onososen, Adetayo & Musonda, Innocent & Onatayo, Damilola & Tjebane, Motheo & Saka, Abdullahi & Fagbenro, Rasaki. (2023). Impediments to Construction Site Digitalization Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). *Drones*. 7. 10.3390/drones7010045.

Royal institute of British Architect (2007) Royal institute of British Architect chartered practice health and safety policy template. *Guidance notes pg 2*

Serena (N.D) How to develop a health and safety policy. *E-how contributor, ehow.com*

Smallwood and Haupt (2005) The need for Health and Safety and the construction regulations: engineers perception. *Journal of the south African institution of civil engineering, Vol 47 No 2 pg 2-8*

Workplace Health and Safety guide (2011) Building and construction Industry workplace Health and Safety guide (Orange book). *Department of Justice and Attorney General Handbook, PN10129 version 3*